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OTEC Resource Assessment of Gulf of Mexico and Surrounding Area

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Abstract

Regarding global interest in marine renewable energy and advancing technologies, Ocean Thermal Energy Conversion (OTEC) stands out as a compelling solution for powering coastal communities, driving the progress of Small Island Developing States (SIDS), and catalyzing blue economy sectors like seawater mining and offshore aquaculture. Flourishing in regions characterized by notable temperature differentials, such as the Gulf of Mexico and Caribbean waters, OTEC has garnered significant attention. Drawing insights from the HYbrid Coordinate Ocean Model (HYCOM) data, this paper presents an OTEC resource assessment covering the Gulf of Mexico, Florida Straits, and Puerto Rico/US Virgin Islands, exploring depths reaching 1500 m throughout the entire year of 2021. The analysis identifies promising OTEC areas and presents a foundation for future OTEC analyses and system design.

Keywords: Ocean Thermal Energy Conversion (OTEC); Resource Assessment; Hybrid Coordinate Ocean Model (HYCOM); Gulf of Mexico

1. Introduction

In the pursuit of sustainable energy solutions, considerable attention has converged on the ocean's capacity to yield power through mechanical forces like currents, waves, and tides, as well as the thermal gradient spanning surface and deep waters [1]. Solar energy absorption in the ocean's upper layer creates warm near-surface waters in many tropical and sub-tropical regions, fostering substantial thermal differentials between this and deep seawater cooled in polar regions [2]. Utilizing this temperature gradient, Ocean Thermal Energy Conversion (OTEC) technology emerges, deriving conceptual roots from Jacques-Arsene d'Arsonval in 1881 [3]. This technology's evolution starts with early endeavors by figures like Georges Claude in the 1930s, to recent milestones like Makai Ocean Engineering's OTEC plant [4,5].

Beyond its energy generation, OTEC bears broader implications across societal, environmental, and economic dimensions. As a catalyst for the blue economy and a mitigator of carbon emissions, OTEC fosters resilience and sustainable development. This study builds upon a foundation [6] for OTEC deployment through exploration of OTEC potential across the Gulf of Mexico, Florida Straits, and Puerto Rico/US Virgin Islands, supported by the HYbrid Coordinate Ocean Model (HYCOM) dataset. Evaluating up to 1500 m deep, the analysis identifies promising OTEC-rich locations.

2. Data and Materials

A data processing strategy is implemented focusing on the computation of temperature difference ΔT between the comparatively warmer surface waters situated at a depth of 20m, and the relatively colder waters at varying depths, ranging from 100 to 1500m. This analysis spans the entire year of 2021, evaluating daily temperature data to provide the basis for calculating essential statistical measures, including the mean, minimum, and standard deviation, all specific to various locations and depths. Locations characterized by a mean ΔT exceeding $\sim 20^\circ\text{C}$ indicate the viability of near-continuous OTEC operations, with higher mean ΔT values suggesting greater efficiency and improved power generation capabilities. Locations that yield a minimum ΔT value surpassing the $\sim 20^\circ\text{C}$ threshold demonstrate potential for continuous energy production throughout the year. The standard deviation provides information about the variability of the temperature gradient throughout the year, showing which areas are more stable.

Given that HYCOM data are available in increments of 100 m up to 1000 m, linear interpolation is employed to estimate temperature data for depths beyond this range (1100m, 1200m, 1300m, and 1400m) from HYCOM data at 1000m, 1250m, and 1500m. To address temperature data gaps, interpolation is employed, utilizing the spring metaphor interpolation method from [7]. Bathymetric data is sourced from GEBCO [8]. The determination of the horizontal area associated with specific coordinates is calculated to approximate the squared area by considering latitude and longitude resolutions according to [9], with the length of 1° of latitude at any location equal to about 111.325 km. The data used to assess the Gulf of Mexico and Florida Straits has a spatial resolution of 0.04° lat x 0.04° lon while the data used to assess Puerto Rico/US Virgin Islands has a resolution of 0.04° lat x 0.08° lon, resulting in an area per coordinate of approximately 18.07 km² and 37.69 km² respectively.

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3. Gulf of Mexico

The thermal resource in the Gulf of Mexico Region is assessed, covering longitudes from -98.00°W to -80.00°W and latitudes from 18.12°N to 31.92°N . The analysis involves the ΔT computed between the warm shallow water temperature at a depth of 20 m and the colder deep-water temperatures. Figures 1, 2, and 3 illustrate the evaluation of ΔT at specific depths ($T_D = 500\text{m}, 1000\text{m}, 1500\text{m}$), focusing on the temporal average, minimum, and standard deviation of ΔT . A more comprehensive depth assessment along with the highest minimum ΔT locations are outlined in Table 1, which provides an overview of the collective area in the Gulf of Mexico surpassing three distinct minimum ΔT thresholds at varying depths. This table shows that there exists a spot in Batabanos Bay, Cuba that has a minimum ΔT of 28.29°C at 200m. This data was investigated and it was verified that this location does have higher than average surface temperatures [10].

Figure 1: Gulf of Mexico Average ΔT .

In the Gulf of Mexico Region, a small area to the east of the Yucatan Peninsula has an average ΔT of approximately 20°C at a depth of 500 m, with a comparable location southeast of the Florida Keys. There is an area of roughly $268,430\text{ km}^2$ with an average ΔT exceeding 18°C , with subsets of 325 km^2 and 18 km^2 sustaining average ΔT of 20°C and 22°C respectively. The maximum average ΔT at this depth is 22.52°C . Deeper assessments at 1000 m reveal an extensive area with an average ΔT surpassing 20°C , except for a small area southeast of Louisiana, where ΔT ranges from 19.00°C to 20.00°C . The highest mean ΔT at 1000 m is 24.10°C . Evaluating a depth of 1500 m confirms that the entire Gulf of Mexico at depths of 1500 m sustains a ΔT characterized by mean temperature differences ranging from 20.00°C to 24.22°C .

Figure 2: Gulf of Mexico Minimum ΔT .

Figure 2 illustrates the minimum ΔT values computed between 20m and the same three cold-water intake depths. No locations have a minimum ΔT exceeding 20°C at 500m. A region extending northeast from the Yucatan Peninsula to Cuba has a minimum ΔT exceeding 20°C at a depth of 1000m, with three points at $18.76^{\circ}\text{N} - 84.08^{\circ}\text{W}$, $19.16^{\circ}\text{N} - 87.00^{\circ}\text{W}$, and $19.16^{\circ}\text{N} - 86.96^{\circ}\text{W}$ that exceed 22°C . This same region maintains a minimum ΔT greater than 22°C at 1500m, covering approximately $131,983\text{ km}^2$, and has the smallest temperature fluctuations throughout the year (Figure 3), evaluated using standard deviation.

Figure 3: Gulf of Mexico Standard Deviation ΔT .

4. Florida Straits

This section performs a similar examination and analysis of the thermal resources in the Florida Straits region, spanning from longitude -84°W to -78.78°W and the latitude range 22°N to 26°N . The Florida Straits overall has shallower depths, averaging approximately 800m, in contrast to the adjacent waters.

Two locations exceeding 20°C average ΔT at 500m are identified at latitude $23.04^{\circ}\text{N} - 82.88^{\circ}\text{W}$ and $24.40^{\circ}\text{N} - 80.56^{\circ}\text{W}$, positioned approximately 260 km and 61 km off Marathon, FL respectively. At this depth, the total area, as outlined in Table 2, is $14,456\text{ km}^2$ with an average ΔT exceeding 18°C . The highest mean ΔT of 22.52°C is observed at a depth of 500m, located at $19.64^{\circ}\text{W} - 80.12^{\circ}\text{N}$. Given the relatively shallow nature of the Florida Straits, the assessment considers a smaller area north of Cuba, $45,124\text{ km}^2$, at depths exceeding 1000m. Most of the region has an average ΔT of at least 20.00°C , with $30,032\text{ km}^2$ having an average ΔT of at least 22°C . A deeper evaluation down to 1500m reveals an area of approximately $17,510\text{ km}^2$ suitable for OTEC (average ΔT of at least 20°C).

Gulf of Mexico – Area of Average ΔT				Gulf of Mexico – Area of Minimum ΔT				Gulf of Mexico – Greatest Minimum ΔT			
Depth (m)	18°C (km ²)	20°C (km ²)	22°C (km ²)	Depth (m)	16°C (km ²)	18°C (km ²)	20°C (km ²)	Depth (m)	Max of min ΔT (°C)	Location	
										lon°W	lat°N
100	0	0	0	100	0	0	0	100	5.64	-87.32	20.16
200	198.77	198.77	198.77	200	198.77	198.77	198.77	200	28.29	-81.72	22.56
300	90.350	0	0	300	0	0	0	300	13.94	-86.72	20.52
400	379.47	54.21	0	400	0	0	0	400	15.39	-86.76	20.44
500	268430	325.26	18.07	500	5222.2	18.070	0	500	18.30	-84.4	22.56
600	972546	41904	162.63	600	105420	2710.5	0	600	19.28	-87	19.12
700	1194156	474445	307.19	700	512664	59883	0	700	19.90	-87.32	19.56
800	1176032	1072509	17726	800	749886	358671	16190	800	20.97	-83.48	21.88
900	1149884	1133079	332722	900	525602	444973	232253	900	21.39	-87.52	18.24
1000	1124406	1115407	593997	1000	957041	482396	303648	1000	22.11	-86.96	19.16
1100	1051367	1046632	650954	1100	949578	471934	319116	1100	22.13	-87.08	18.28
1200	1051367	1047807	748767	1200	987633	506429	344034	1200	22.46	-83.96	18.16
1300	983785	982122	759536	1300	956083	501713	336210	1300	22.63	-83.96	18.16
1400	983785	982411	786750	1400	959715	528655	338433	1400	22.63	-83.96	18.16
1500	983785	982791	806735	1500	962625	559411	341216	1500	22.66	-87	18.52

Table 1: Gulf of Mexico Area of Average ΔT (Left) and Minimum ΔT (Center) exceeding 3 thresholds and information on Greatest Minimum ΔT (Right).

Figure 4: Florida Straits Average ΔT .

Figure 5 shows that at 500m depth there are no locations with a minimum ΔT exceeding 18°C, yet four distinct locations exhibit a minimum ΔT exceeding 16°C, three of which are clustered near 24.56°N -80.36°W, and one at 24.88°N -80.08°W. At 1000m, an area of 3,144 km² has a minimum ΔT exceeding 20.00°C. Similarly, the 1500m depth in the same area comprises 11,872 km² above this threshold. The Florida Straits has two locations with minimum ΔT exceeding 18°C at 700m: 23.00°N -83.40°W and 23.20°N -82.32°W, with variability assessed in (Figure 6).

Figure 5: Florida Straits Minimum ΔT .

Figure 6: Florida Straits Standard Deviation ΔT .

Florida Straits - Area of Average ΔT				Florida Straits - Area of Minimum ΔT				Florida Straits - Greatest Minimum ΔT			
Depth (m)	18°C (km ²)	20°C (km ²)	22°C (km ²)	Depth (m)	16°C (km ²)	18°C (km ²)	20°C (km ²)	Depth (m)	Max of min ΔT (°C)	Location	
										lon°W	lat°N
100	0	0	0	100	0	0	0	100	1.76	-79.88	27.24
200	0	0	0	200	0	0	0	200	28.29	-81.72	22.56
300	18.070	0	0	300	0	0	0	300	12.56	-80.08	25.04
400	144.56	0	0	400	0	0	0	400	14.36	-80.12	24.88
500	14456	36.140	0	500	72.280	0	0	500	16.53	-80.08	24.88
600	38633	921.57	0	600	1445.6	0	0	600	17.57	-80.24	24.6
700	47650	27538	18.070	700	38236	36.140	0	700	18.98	-83.4	23
800	43910	42843	54.210	800	43422	16859	0	800	18.71	-82.32	23.2
900	39121	38995	1590.2	900	39067	29454	0	900	19.56	-80.56	22
1000	34911	34893	30032	1000	34911	30592	3144.2	1000	20.83	-86.96	23.04
1100	25569	25569	25153	1100	25569	2443	11366	1100	20.44	-83.76	23.12
1200	25569	25569	25298	1200	25569	24719	13299	1200	20.84	-82.64	23.2
1300	17509	17509	17509	1300	17509	17256	11203	1300	21.10	-82.48	23.24
1400	17509	17509	17509	1400	17509	17311	11564	1400	21.14	-81.76	23.52
1500	17509	17509	17509	1500	17509	17347	11871	1500	21.29	-81.64	23.52

Table 2: Florida Straits Area of Average ΔT (Left) and Minimum ΔT (Center) exceeding 3 thresholds and information on Greatest Minimum ΔT (Right).

5. Puerto Rico / US Virgin Islands

This section analyzes the thermal resources in the Puerto Rico and US Virgin Islands region, at longitudes from -67.50°W to -64.50°W and the latitude range 16.50°N to 20.00°N. The waters surrounding Puerto Rico have a rapid increase in depth near the shore, particularly to the north in the Puerto Rico Trench.

Figure 7 shows the average ΔT between 20m and three cold water depths, and Table 3 presents the cumulative area surrounding Puerto Rico where three distinct reference mean ΔT thresholds are surpassed at different depths. Particularly noteworthy are areas with mean ΔT exceeding 18°C at relatively shallow depths like 300m, covering 226 km².

Figure 7: Puerto Rico and US Virgin Islands Average ΔT .

Several locations around the islands have an average ΔT exceeding 22°C at a depth of 500m. The highest mean ΔT at 500m depth is 23.61°C, at 19.08°N and longitude 64.64°W. At 1000m depth, nearly all surrounding waters, 105,456 km², have an average ΔT exceeding 20.00°C, and an area totaling 55,103 km² with an average ΔT of at least 22°C. Extending the assessment to depths of up to 1500m, the entire region has an average ΔT exceeding 20.00°C.

Figure 8: Puerto Rico and the US Virgin Islands Minimum ΔT .

Figure 8 illustrates the minimum ΔT between 20m and the same 3 cold water intake depths, while Figure 9 provides the standard deviation of ΔT . No locations have a minimum 18°C exceeding ΔT at 500m; however, there are four distinct areas, with a total area of 151 km², primarily centered around 18.52°N and longitude -64.24°W, with a minimum ΔT exceeding 16°C. At 1000m, an area of around 54,952 km² exceeds a

minimum ΔT of 20°C. Notably, the southern side of the island demonstrates slightly elevated ΔT values at this depth. Similarly, at 1500m, 10,0067 km² maintains a minimum ΔT greater than 20°C, consistently found from 1300m depths.

Figure 9: Puerto Rico and US Virgin Islands Standard Deviation ΔT .

Puerto Rico and US Virgin Islands – Area of Average ΔT				Puerto Rico and US Virgin Islands – Area of Minimum ΔT				Puerto Rico and US Virgin Islands – Greatest Min ΔT			
Depth (m)	Area of Average ΔT			Depth (m)	Area of Minimum ΔT			Depth (m)	Max of min ΔT (°C)	Location	
	18°C (km ²)	20°C (km ²)	22°C (km ²)		16°C (km ²)	18°C (km ²)	20°C (km ²)			lon°W	lat°N
100	0	0	0	100	0	0	0	100	2.39	-67.28	17.92
200	0	0	0	200	0	0	0	200	7.93	-65.04	18.56
300	226.14	75.380	37.690	300	0	0	0	300	15.78	-65.60	18.48
400	565.35	339.21	188.45	400	0	0	0	400	15.37	-64.64	17.8
500	942.25	489.97	113.07	500	150.76	0	0	500	17.84	-64.56	18.8
600	54047	904.56	188.45	600	50127	226.14	37.690	600	20.38	-66.88	18.56
700	105381	49185	489.97	700	90079	46396	113.07	700	21.82	-67.36	17.92
800	107039	71234	640.73	800	106926	67728	301.52	800	21.60	-66.64	17.84
900	106398	106323	3090.58	900	106323	100556	50391	900	22.03	-64.96	18.16
1000	105494	105456	55102.78	1000	105456	105418	54952	1000	22.17	-64.72	17.8
1100	102893	102893	67653.55	1100	102893	102893	75945	1100	21.77	-65.12	18.12
1200	102893	102893	102893.7	1200	102893	102893	212571	1200	21.95	-65.12	18.12
1300	100067	100067	100067	1300	100067	100067	100067	1300	21.99	-64.96	18.12
1400	100067	100067	100067	1400	100067	100067	100067	1400	22.05	-65.76	17.96
1500	100067	100067	100067	1500	100067	100067	100067	1500	22.19	-65.92	17.88

Table 3: Puerto Rico and US Virgin Islands Area of Average ΔT , Area of Minimum ΔT , and Maximum Minimum.

6. Conclusion

OTEC stands as a robust energy source with the potential to energize coastal communities, Small Island Developing States (SIDS), and bolster the blue economy. A comprehensive evaluation of the OTEC resource was conducted across the Gulf of Mexico, Florida Straits, and Puerto Rico / US Virgin Islands. The assessment encompassed depths up to 1500m and considered the temporally averaged mean, minimum, and standard deviation of the thermal resource, and spotlighted noteworthy sites for potential OTEC deployment.

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